

Research Article

Nigeria Treasury and the menace of Kleptocrats

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Abstract

This paper analyses treasury looters in Nigeria since independence. It also itemizes alleged kleptocrats and their offences and Whistle blowers' recovery according to Economic and Financial Crime Commission. As we all aware that Nigerians diamond independence anniversary is two years ahead with one major question disturbing the minds of average Nigeria. The major question is how can kleptocrats be eradicated? The ages of self-government though short, but provides an opportunity to examine how Nigeria is heading to a state of kleptocracy. It is disturbing that kleptocrats are in all ramification their activities can be seen at Local, State and Federal governments as well as private organizations. Again, kleptocrat is seen as an attempt to turn Nigeria to a state of small cabal. The study employed descriptive survey method, with population consisting people of Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted and different stage of sampling when carried out this investigation. Three research questions were generated to guide toward analysis of the results. The results of the study show that the economic predicament of Nigeria is as a result of unchecked mismanagement and embezzlement of nation's fund. To turn the situation around, the paper recommends (i) Inculcating the training of integrity into the school setting right away from primary to secondary and tertiary institutions. (ii) Severe penalty to those find guilty of one act of corruption or the other, among others.

Keywords: Corruption, kleptocrats and treasury.

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Introduction

A Kleptocracy is a form of political and government corruption where the government exists to increase the personal wealth and political power of its officials and the ruling class at the expense of the wider population often with pretense of honest service. Onimode (2001) sees Kleptocracy as that type of government where corruption is often achieved by the embezzlement of state funds. He argues that it is amazing that in Nigeria the era of kleptocrats begins as far back as the era of military junta of General Ibrahim Babangida. It is obvious that since 1999, Nigeria treasury has been looted compared the military regimes. It is also disturbing that while the stealing continues, the primary schools are in shambles, there is no primary health care, there is a hike in Universities fees, roads are poor condition and there is no pipe borne water. The health systems favour the kleptocracy very well because they access health facilities abroad.

It is about taking advantage of corruption to extend their personal wealth and political power. Basically, this system involves the embezzlement of state funds at the expense of the wider population, sometimes without even the disguise of honest service. It is a system where leaders make themselves rich and powerful by stealing from the rest of the people. It is generally associated with dictatorships oligarchy, military juntas or other forms of autocratic and nepotism government in which external oversight is possible or does not exist. They usually treat their country's treasury as a source of personal wealth, spending funds on luxury goods and extravagance as they deem fit. They usually transfer the public fund into hidden personal bank accounts in foreign countries to provide for themselves if removed from power. Kleptocracy is an uncountable form of corrupt government that allows the ruling class to accumulate great wealth and power while neglecting the mass of citizens.

It is surprising to see Nigeria which is giant of Africa, to witness regime that differs to the foundation of what our founding fathers laid down. Nigeria that is a state of milk and honey now a state of thieves that get power in federal, state and local government. Nigeria is a state of abundant resources such as crude oil, limestone, power, energy, marble, backed up with vast population of 170 million (Population Census 2006) Nigeria is now becoming a state of kleptocrats where average Nigeria only has access to one square meal per day but the kleptocrats compete on who builds the best marble houses with looted funds. They compete on who is rated as having looted more billions of dollars, pounds and naira at the expenses of the masses. In contrary, average Nigeria lived below \$2 per day. (World Bank Reports 2012). Nigeria is a state where dividend of democracy is often not felt by ordinary Nigerians on the streets, largely because the first pre-occupation of elected politicians on assuming office is to recoup the expenses they

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incurred during the electioneering period in multi fold. Nigeria loses \$10 billion annually to treasury looting (UNDDC 2009). Nigeria has lost about \$550 billion to treasury looters in her 57 years of independence. Nigeria is becoming a small cabal of powerful individuals have hijacked the whole democratic initiative for self-seeking interests. This notion is contrary to the tenants of democracy that premises on equality, social justices, constitutionalism, freedom, sovereignty, etc.

This syndrome is most common in developing countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Togo, Sudan, Liberia, and Syria whose economies are based on the export of natural resources. Such export income constitutes a form of economic rent and is easier to siphon off without causing the income to decrease. The effect of such practice affects welfare of the state in economy, political affairs and civil right. It ruins prospects of foreign investment and drastically weakens the domestic market and cross the border. The syndrome is not in Nigeria alone, according to NGO Transparency International 2014. The following were looted treasury of their Country with huge amount of money ranging from Pound Sterling to Dollars and Naira: former Indonesian president Suharto \$15vbillion -35, former Philippine president Ferdinand Marcus \$216 billion, former Congolese president Mobutu Sese Seko \$5 billion, former Nigeria Head of State Sanni Abacha \$2 - \$5 billion, former Yugoslavia president Sloboda Minsevic \$1 billion, former Hartian president Jean Chard Duualies \$300 - 800 million, former Peruvian president Albert Fujinuri \$600 million, former Ukrainian prime minister Pavio Lazarenko \$200 million, former Nicaraguan president Arnolodo Alema \$100 million, former Philippine president Joseph Estrada \$78 - 80 million, former Russian president Vladimir Putin \$200 billion, Egyptian president Mosir Mubarak \$70 billion, Plochama Yasir Arafat \$10 billion, Pakistan president Asif - Ali Zardari \$2 billion, Head of Kazakhstan Nwrsulta Nazarbayeu and former China prime minister Wen Siabaw \$2.7 billion

In summary, Nigeria should be a state where whole of Nigerian enjoying democracy. Democracy is a system of government where governing power is derived from the people either by direct democracy or by means of elected representatives. Basically, the usurpers of democracy have stolen democracy away from the good people of Nigeria, and its place has forcefully entrenched kleptocracy. Democracy will gain its status if fairness and equity are allowed to thrive in the sharing and administration of public fund and resources.

Statement of Problem

A thorough examination of Nigeria since 1960 when she obtained her independence will end up to discover that the dreams of the founding fathers are not in reality in the area of political and economic development. Chinua Achebe (1993) argues that the

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visions of the founding fathers for grouping themselves together and chased away colonial master out of the country were at very far and per to what we are witnessing. Though there are numbers of factors that contributed to this imbalance between the visions of the founding fathers and the so called leaders of today. Among these factors are lack of internal democracy, party politics, external factor, lack of integrity and debts, among others. In this paper, the researchers focus on the attitude and characters of leaders that can be regarded as Kleptocrats. The investigation was apparently carried out sequence to mode of mismanagement of billions of Dollars for personal interest and fear of unknown. This is in line with the finding of British Banks (1985) on looted funds being kept into their custody.

This study tried to examine the opinion of the people on the attitudes and styles of leaders in Nigeria. The study examined how billions of Dollars and Pound Sterling were looted into the hands of Kleptocrats, and imbalance in the sharing and administration of national resources. The menace has aggravated poverty level and subjected Nigerian leadership to a mere avenue of sharing of national cake.

Aim of the Study

To pursue vividly the extent by which Leaders are looting Nigeria treasury since 1960 and possible checks on the pressure.

Analysis of alleged treasury looters in Nigeria since Independence

Nnamdi Azikwe was the first major political figure investigated for questionable practices. Babawale (2006) states that in 1944, a firm belonging to Azikwe and family bought a Bank in Lagos and most of the paid up capital of the African Continental Bank were from the Eastern Regional Financial Corporation. While Babatunde (1999), emphasis that Adegoke Adelabu was investigated following charges of political corruption leveled against him by the opposition and how this led to demand his resignation as District Council Head and spell out allegations that were leveled against some native authority officials in Bornu.

During Gowon administration August 1966 - July 1975, corruption was kept away from public view until 1975. Turner (1976) emphasis that a corruption scandal surrounding the importation of cement by many officials of the Defense Ministry and the Central Bank of Nigeria. Again two individual from the Middle Belt were accused of corruption. During Obasanjo administration from February 1976 - September 1979, went to the transition programme to democracy as well as implementing the national development plans. Keith (1980) argues that a number of national projects were conducted to distribute favours and enrich connected politician as Fela Anikulapo Kuti

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sang variously about major scandals involving the international tele-communication friction ITT led by Chief MKO Abiola which Olusegun Obasanjo was associated with Operation Feed the Nation Programme while Olajide (1977) concludes that Land grab under the Land Use Decree was on an assignment to reward cronies.

In Shagari administration of October 1979 - December 1983, Leon (!983) explains that few federal buildings mysteriously went on fire after investigators started probe on the finance of the officials building. He seizes Defunct Johnson Mathey Bank of London acted as a conduct to transfer hard currencies for some party members in Nigeria and concludes that rice shortage led to the accusation of corruption against NPN government. During Buhari administration of December 1983 - August 1985, cross section of political gladiators was convicted of different forms of corrupt practice. Azikwe (2016) obliges that there was suit cases scandal that coincidentally involved Atiku Abubakar. He saw Atiku Abubakar being indicted for various acts of corruption. He reminded us about the 53 Suit cases say arouse in 1984 during currency change exercise. It was ordered that every case arriving the country should be inspected irrespective of the status of the person behind such. It was unfortunate that the 53 Suit cases were ferried through the Muritala Muhammed Airport without Customs checked by soldiers allegedly at the behest of Major Mustapha Jokolo the Aide-De-Camp (ADC) to General Buhari. Atiku was at that time the area comptroller of Custom in charge of the Muritala Muhammed Airport he concluded.

During Babagida administration from August 1985 - August 1983, he legalized corruption and his administration refused to give an account of Gulf War which has been established to be \$12.4b. He rigged the only successful election June 12, 1993. He lives in an exquisite mansion. Corruption has elevated to the policy of state. Vehicles and cash gifts were routinely disbursed. There were IBB boys, dirty deals from drugs, money laundering, drug dealing through first Lady Mariam Babangida and Gloria Okon (girlfriend) through the revelation from Dele Giwa. There was assassination of a journalist through letter bomb, privatization to reward friend's investment in Globalcom

During Abacha administration from November 1993 - June 1998, Hector (2004) explains that there were bribes paid to government officials ease the award of a gas plant construction in Nigeria. He continues to see the investigation led to freezing of account containing about and \$100m. Hector emphasis that Swiss Banking Commission report indicted Swiss Bank for failing to follow compliance process in allowing family and friends of Abacha to access to account and depositing amount totally \$600m into the account. While, David (2000), argues that total sums of \$1b were found in various

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accounts throughout Europe belonging to Abacha. During Abdulsalam Abubakar administration from June 1998 - May 1999, a huge of wealth was acquired by him and his inner circle. He lives in exquisite mansion. Also the major Halliburton scandal implicated his administration.

During Olusegun Obasanjo administration from May 1999 - May 2007, his Vice President Atiku Abubakar was caught in cohort with US Congressman with cold hard cash literally in freezers. The ICBR and Siemens bribery scandals were seriously investigated by the FBI and there were various international indictments that indicated high level corruption in his administration. There was \$65b Liquefied National Gas scandal. There was Transcorp Shares scandals and Presidential Library donations at the eve of his exit from power and tried to alter constitution to get third term ticket (Vanguard News 22 May 2011).

During Umaru Musa Yar Adua administration from May 2007 - May 2010, Attorney General Aondokaa frustrated the ongoing local and international investigations of his powerful friends like Governors James Ibori, Igbinnedion and Peter Odilli. Wiki leaks revealed that Supreme Court Judges were bribed to legitimize the corrupt election that saw him to emerging as president through massive rigging. There were illegal payments from NNPC to president (Vanguard News 2 July 2016).

During Goodluck Jonathan administration from May 2010 - May 2015, Tim Cocks and Joe Brock (2015) stated that NNPC failed to remit \$20b of Oil revenues and see running scandals that involve the BMW purchase by his Aviation Minister at \$250m. Chima (2014) explains that there were security contracts to militants in the Niger Delta, massive corruptions, kick back in Ministry of Petroleum, Malibo Oil and International scandal and question Central Bank scandal of cash in 4days, where ₦8b was stolen.

Finally, we are also pleased to explain that new allegations of corruption have begun to emerge since the departure of President Jonathan on May 29, 2015 and these are:

1. \$2.2 b illegally withdrawn from, excess crude oil account and \$1b was approved by President to fund his re-election without the knowledge of National Economic Council that made up of State Governors and the President and Vice President.
2. NETTI discovered \$11.6Billion missing from Nigeria LNG Company dividend payment.
3. 60m barrels of oil valued at \$13.7b was stolen under the watch of the National Oil Giant of Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation from 2001 to 2012.
4. \$11.63b paid to the NNPC without the evident of the money being remitted to the federation account.

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5. Diversion 60% of \$1b foreign loans obtained from the Chinese by Ministry of Finance
6. Misuse of 3trillion naira defense budget through massive scam in weapons and defense procurement. see <http://campuswaka.com/2015/07/05tensioninmilitaryasbuharidemandrecordofweaponsprocurement>
7. Diversion of \$2.2m Vaccination Medicine fund by Ministry of Health (nigeria's ministry of health mismanagement \$2.2million meant for vaccination).
8. Diversion of Ebola fight fund up to ₦1.9b and NIMASA fraud totaling ₦43b (#1.9Billion ebola fund scam).
9. \$2.2m to Health Ministry through Minister of Finance Okonjo Iweala (okonjo iweala connected with fresh \$2.2million trouble).
10. NDDC scams and multifarious scams including ₦2.7 b without confirmation to public procurement Acts (51).

Whistle blowers' recovery in Nigeria by Economic and Financial Crime Commission:

1. \$9.7m (#2985.567.689) had been found in slums of Sabon Tasha area of Kaduna
2. ₦400m in Lagos plaza shop
3. ₦250m (\$816.062) in Balogun Market in Lagos
4. ₦55.8b stashed in Banks
5. ₦49m (₦160, 340) found in Kaduna airport
6. \$43.4m, £27,800m and ₦23.2 in Ikoyi Lagos States
7. Unidentified man pays ₦42m as tithe in one Local Church in Makurdi, Benue State.

The following questions must strictly proffer urgent solutions for our proper understanding of the reasons behind peoples looting the treasure of their Nation States. Where is the source of this money? What is the nature of the business these people are doing? Are these people so too big that law cannot catch them? What type of legacy looters are leaving behind for in coming generations to emulate? How does spillover effect of looting treasure of a Nation States will be?

Method

This study is a descriptive survey research. The population of this study consisted of people in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State. The target population for this study was Civil Servants in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted and different stage of sampling when carried out this investigation. Basically Civil Servants in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State were clustered into categories of Group A and Group B

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respectively. Group A comprises Teachers and Local Government Workers while Group B comprises LAUTECH Staff and LAUTECH Teaching Hospital Staff. Proportionate sampling technique was adopted in the selection of 387 respondents from the two groups.

A research's designed questionnaire with content validity which was ascertained by the experts in the field of this study who made possible alteration and suggestions was used to collate needed data. Test retest reliability method was used with a sample of 40:60:120:167 respondents in Group A Teachers (40), Local Government Workers (60), and Group B LAUTECH Staff (120) and LAUTECH Teaching Hospital Staff (167) of the people of Ogbomoso South local government area of Oyo State respectively with four week interval. The scores of the first test were correlated with the second test using Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and a reliability index of 0.84 was obtained. The research questions were raised for this study and answered with percentage, mean and standard deviation and bar chart was used to illustrate the results.

Research Questions

Researchers raised three research questions to guide the investigation.

1. How frequent is public funds are looted into the hands of Leaders in Nigeria since 1960?
2. Does Leaders turn Nigeria to a State of Kleptocracy?
3. What is the opinion of the people on how Kleptocrats wasted billions of Dollars and Pound Sterling on the personal interest and fear of unknown?

Data Analysis

Researchers' analyzed data collated thoroughly and answered the research questions raised in the course of their investigation.

Research Question 1: *How frequent do public funds are wasted into the hands of leaders since 1960?*

Data was collected from the questionnaire and research question 1 was answered using percentage and bar chart. The outcome of the analysis was presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 showing the frequency of how public funds are wasting in the hands of leaders in Nigeria since 1960

Figure 1 revealed that a high frequency of respondents sampled, 315(81.4%) agreed that public funds are customarily wasted into the hands of leaders in Nigeria. Also 35(9%) submitted that it was based on systematic, while 21(5.4%) submitted that it was based on monthly and the remaining concluded that 16(4.1%) was on often basis instead to use the money to provide social infrastructure for the benefits of masses in Nigeria. These submissions agreed with World Bank Report (2012) and Hector (2004) when argued extremely on freezes of \$100m and Nigeria investigation of looted funds.

Research Question 2: *To what extent was leaders turn Nigeria to a State of Kleptocracy?*

Research Question 2 was answered using mean and standard deviation with the data from the instrument and result revealed in Table 1.

Table 1 showing how Leaders turn Nigeria to a State of Kleptocracy.

Ruining Nigeria's Economy	Responses	Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranking
God fatherism noticeable among thirty six states of the federation	184	1.99	088	1 ST
Receiving big Contracts without implementation	170	1.95	216	2 nd
Influencing government policies and decisions to favour their allies	148	1.93	264	3 rd
Owing largest percentages of Shares in Blue Chip Companies.	125	1.92	272	4 th
Unconstitutional removal of disobedient political sons and daughters from office	119	1.88	327	5 th
Engaging in corrupt practices	118	1.84	362	6 th
Awarding Contracts to sons, daughters and relatives without any implementations	113	1.78	416	7 th
Diverting treasure of nation without minding the spillover effect on the masses	101	1.76	429	8 th
Sponsoring candidates to win an election at all cost.	94	1.74	440	9 th
Hidden hard Currencies in soak ways, tankers and under construction projects	86	1.71	455	10 th
Using billions of dollars and pound sterling to construct refineries in developing nations of the world	60	1.70	461	11 th
Holding different accounts in foreign countries	43	1.69	462	12 th
Fighting corruption back at all cost	31	1.68	468	13 th
Construction of estates, mansions and giants houses in all State capitals of the federation	29	1.62	487	14 th
Cross carpeting from one political party to another	19	1.56	497	15 th
Causing militants such as Boko Haram, Fulani Headsmen and Niger Delta Avenger	3	1.52	500	16 th

Table 1 illustrates that leaders turns Nigeria to a State of Kleptocracy through the act of godfatherism as it gained a mean score of 1.99 and ranked highest. Receiving big contracts and influencing government policies and decisions had a mean score of 1.95(2nd) and 1.93(3rd) respectively. While fighting corruption back at all cost, construction of estates, mansion and giants houses and cross carpeting from one political party to another had a mean scores of 1.68, 1.62, 1.56, and ranked 13th, 14th and 15th respectively. Essentially, it implies that leaders in Nigeria are ruining economy through their act of stealing from the treasure of the federation. Our submission agreed with David (2000) and UNDDC (2009) on missing millions in the developing countries during their investigations.

Research Question 3: *What is the opinion of the masses on how leaders wasted billions of dollars and pound sterling on personal interest and fear of unknown?*

Data was collected from the questionnaire to answer research question 3, using percentage and bar chart and the result was presented in Table 2 and Figure 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2 showing opinions of the masses on how Leaders in Nigeria wasted billions of Dollars and Pound Sterling.

Opinion on wasted billions of Dollars and Pound Sterling	Frequency	Percentage
YES	100	25.83
To reduce the power of leaders	26	26
To eradicate corrupt practices and godfatherism	43	43
To implement anti-corruption and anti-graft bills	31	31
NO	287	74.16
Politicking of leaders in Nigeria without minding any negative effect of spill over	128	41.7
Anti-corruption and anti-graft Bills should stop at first reading.	159	58.3
TOTAL	387	100

Figure 2 showing the submission of respondents who want to reduce and eradicate the power of Leaders in Nigeria through Constitutional means.

Figure 3 showing the submission of respondents, on those that do not want a reduction in the powers of Leaders through Constitutional means

Table 2, figure 2 and 3 revealed that out of 387 respondents sampled, 100(25.83%) submitted that there should be reductions in the power of Leaders in Nigeria While 287(74.17%) submitted that there should be Anti-Corruption and Anti-Graft Bills in all levels of government. Out of the 100 (25.83%) respondents sampled submitted that reduction in power of leaders (43-42.5%); eradication of corrupt practices and godfatherism (31-31%); and Anti-graft bills (26-26.5%) On the other hand, out of the 287(74.17%) respondents sampled submitted that anti-graft bills should stop at first reading (159-58.3%); politicking without minding the spillover effect and (128-41.7%) It is obvious that majority of people in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State submitted that Leaders trying as much as possible to turn Nigeria to a State of Kleptocracy.

Result of Findings

It is obvious, Kleptocrats in Nigeria cut across all six geo-political zones of the federation (North East, North Central, North West, South West, South East and South South) Again, they vary from sector to another. They are well recognized in the three arm of government (the Legislature, the Executive and the Judiciary) they are notable very well in three tiers of government (local, state and federal) They are traceable enough among the Militants, Para Military, traditional rulers, religious leaders, public servants and off course Kleptocrats are present everywhere there is average of 1 - 50 people in Nigeria. Therefore, it is clearly seen that the only trouble with Nigeria since independence is Kleptocrats through their corrupt practices. In sum our finding reveals that the Story Report, World Bank Report (2012), UNDDC (2009) and other investigations on the looted money in Nigeria were accurate and to a larger extent realistic for further investigation by researcher.

Conclusion

If what Martin Luther Jn. predicted and emphasized in his Dream Speech of 28 August 1963 came to feasible and reality after 45 years in America and Africa America became President of United States of America for the first time and we are sure that a day will come when Nigeria will become a free State where there is no room for marginalization in any means or in any form. We have no doubt that Nigeria will become a State where education is free in primary, secondary and tertiary institutions respectively. We are convincing that Nigeria will not experience total black out for a single day but the country will celebrate no power inter-erupted like our dear sister Country Ghana for a solid year. We are optimistic that one day sons and daughters of poor farmers will dine

and wine inside the Aso Rock where the seat of Mr. President located. We are pleased to see the forgotten and neglected sons and daughters in Nigeria to take up the cap and rule the entire nation successfully without any act of regionalism and tribalism. We are of opinion that Nigeria roads will be freed of death traps and the rich and wealthy people will not have any reasons to travel abroad for medical attention. We are strongly believed that a day is far approaching when Nigeria will become semi – paradise where technology is okay, industry is very palatable, social infrastructure is something to write home about, adequate security when men and women can sleep with their two eyes closed, when one naira will equal one dollar, and Nigeria will become tourism centre where global village will come and showcase and transact their businesses and products, when there will be economic and political freedom from ex-while colonial master and freedom from hand of kleptocrats who retards the growth and development of entire nation.

Summarily, a day is moving closer when the massacre of kleptocrats in Nigeria will be feasible and the Federal Republic of Nigeria will have peace in all ramifications as illustrated when the Ball prophets executed in Israel by Prophet Elijah and Jehu.

Recommendations

At the end of critical investigation by the researchers and a thoroughly analysis of the actions and practices of Kleptocrats in Nigeria, the researchers hereby suggested the followings as way out to find lasting solution to the only trouble brought by Kleptocrats through their corrupt practices.

1. Inculcating the training of integrity into the school setting right away from primary to secondary and tertiary institutions.
2. Severe penalty to those found guilty of one act of corruption or the other.
3. Judiciary and other Economic Crime Commission and Inquiry such as EFFC, ICPC, and CCT etc should be independent.
4. Adequate follow up exercise on Whistle Blowers Policy to reward accordingly as stated and promised.
5. International collaboration to report, trial, prosecute and jail Kleptocrats.
6. Dealing with corruption should be moved away from sentiment, tribalism, nepotism, ethnicity and political colouration.
7. Fighting corruption should cut across all sectors such as religious organizations, political parties and economic sectors.

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